

REVIEW

OPEN ACCESS

Advancing Wastewater Management: Policies and Sustainable Solutions for Global Water Security

Simran Jit¹

¹Department of Zoology, Miranda House, University of Delhi, Delhi, 110007, India

²Department of Zoology, Maitreyi College, Babu Dham, Chanakyapuri, New Delhi-110021, India

³Department of Zoology, Hansraj College, University of Delhi, Delhi, 110007, India

*Correspondence for materials should be addressed to MV (email: mansiverma20@gmail.com)

Abstract

In recent years, the mismanaged disposal of waste into water resources has increased, leading to the generation of an estimated 360–380 billion cubic meters (BCM) of wastewater annually across the globe. This wastewater contains a range of harmful and persistent contaminants from agricultural, industrial, and domestic activities, posing significant risks to public health, the environment, and ecosystems. This review highlights the policies implemented by various nations for wastewater disposal and reuse, with a focus on bioremediation technologies adopted by urban regions to address water stress and inconsistencies in water management and discharge practices. The application of newer technologies along with statistical computer systems for predictive modeling and analytics are crucial in achieving sustainable wastewater treatment and reuse. These advancements are critical for mitigating water crises and enabling the safe use of treated wastewater for irrigation, aquaculture, agroforestry, landscaping, aquifer recharge, and even potable purposes. Ultimately, this review underscores the importance of sustainable alternatives in wastewater treatment to combat water pollution and secure water resources for the future.

Keywords: Wastewater treatment plant (WWTP); Contaminants; Policies; Biochar; Bioremediation; Artificial intelligence

Introduction

Many wastewater (WW) products are produced annually around the world due to increased urbanization, industrial development and population expansion (Jones et al., 2021; Qadir et al., 2020). However, only 11% of the total wastewater generated from domestic and industrial sectors is treated, and nearly 50% of the world's untreated wastewater ultimately reach freshwater bodies and seas (www.unep.org). These figures are alarming for this critical and life nurturing resource, and consequently, governments have prioritized innovating and developing wastewater treatment technologies at a larger scale to provide safe water at affordable prices. Additionally, a comprehensive assessment of wastewater production and its treatment for disposal or reuse at the global scale is needed in compliance with SDG 6 (Clean water and sanitation) and SDG 6.3 (Improving Water Quality, Wastewater Treatment and Safe Reuse) as well as United Nations, which specify the importance of achieving improvements in water quality by treating wastewater and promoting its safe reuse. The rise of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) coincides with the quick urbanization and population expansion, industrialization and a substantial increase in the amount of wastewater to be treated efficiently (Delanka-Pedige et al., 2021; Silva, 2023; Villarín and Merel, 2020).

To reuse treated wastewater, removing microcontaminants from wastewater, which can negatively impact our ecosystem, including human health, is important (Aemig et al., 2021; Rogowska et al., 2020). These include antibiotic-resistant pathogens, cosmetics, pharmaceutical residues,

household and industrial chemicals, or other chemicals (Abbas et al., 2022; Kurniawan et al., 2023). Hence, the present review highlights wastewater pollutants, policies implemented by many countries to overcome this issue, and recent advancements and innovations in wastewater treatment. The review also focuses on plausible solutions that may be adopted to make wastewater treatment more efficient and economic.

Common contaminants of wastewater and their implications

Wastewater also referred as “used” water is generally contaminated due to human activities (Mateo-Sagasta et al., 2015). Social water insecurities, natural floods, and domestic and industrial waste management malpractices have resulted in the leaching of contaminants and pollutants into water bodies. The three major sectors that contribute to WW generation are agriculture, industry and domestic (Table 1). Industrial waste, which is rich in organic and inorganic chemicals, comes from various industries, including chemical, cosmetics, food processing and preservation, paper, pulp, leather manufacturing, nuclear and thermal power, textile processing, pharmaceuticals, mines, iron, steel and petroleum refining (Zailani and Sarvajayakesavalu, 2023). Other sources of WW pollutants include sewage leakages; oil spillages; biological discards; leachates from soil due to erosion, and application of fertilizers, herbicides, and pesticides (Ahmed et al., 2021). The organic content in industrial wastes is ~ 1–200 g/L, with a non-neutral pH of variable temperatures, salinity, turbidity, high content of heavy metals, saturation levels of gases, color and odor (Ahmed et al., 2022; Okeke et al., 2021).

Several of the heavy metals (H) such as Cd, Cr, Ni, Zn, Pb, Hg, As and Mn; hazardous chemicals; aromatic compounds; dyes; toxic metals; and pathogenic microorganisms in WW can cause grave health concerns (Hussain et al., 2013; Kim et al., 2024). Additionally, WW can communicate water borne diseases such as cholera, diarrhea, giardiasis, as well as hepatitis, jaundice, typhoid and cancer (Fukunaka et al., 2023). Both Cr(III) and Cr(VI) are known to cause skin irritation and cancer as well as disintegrating the softer tissues of snails and worms (Akpore et al., 2014), whereas in plants, chromium has adverse effects on morphological, biochemical, physiological, molecular and cell signaling (Ali et al., 2023). Additionally, the presence of zinc in WW may increase the acidity of water, which in turn can affect the cultivation and crop yield (Kaur and Garg, 2021). The effluent from sewage increases the alkalinity of WW and the presence of colloidal proteins and polymers to increase the absorption of heavy metals, notably Cu, Zn, Pb, and Cr (Geng et al., 2020; Wei et al., 2019).

In total suspended solids (TSSs) or the suspended sediment concentration (SSC), the optically active inorganic and organic particulate matter with a diameter less than 62 μm , which are elevated by mining processes, often deplete resources for aquatic life (Adjovu et al., 2023; Butler and Ford, 2018; Dey and Vijay, 2021; Jiang et al., 2023) which includes halides, metals, HMs and surface run-offs. While the organic compounds include aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), aliphatic and heterocyclic compounds, herbicides, phenols, polycyclic, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), and pesticides. One such compound, bisphenol A (BPA) (used to produce plastic), is categorized as an endocrine-disrupting chemical (EDC) and can interfere with the endocrine system (Mishra et al., 2023). Excessive amounts of minerals lead to eutrophication and algal blooms, which can pose serious health and environmental hazards (Chahal et al., 2016). Biological contaminants such as water-dwelling human pathogens enter WW from direct defecation or from fecally contaminated domestic waste (Zimmerman et al., 2020). These pathogenic organisms are known to cause various human diseases or disorders, such as gastroenteritis (*Campylobacter jejuni*, *Escherichia coli*, *Yersinia* spp., and *Astrovirus*), salmonellosis, typhoid, paratyphoid (*Salmonella* spp.), diarrhea, anemia, weight loss (*Trichuris trichiura*), and respiratory infections (Chahal et al., 2016). Other important determinants of WW include physico-chemical parameters like temperature, pH, conductivity, saturation levels of gases, color and odor (Okeke et al., 2021).

Generation of wastewater across the globe

Around the world, the treatment of WW has become a major challenge, with about only one tenth of the total volume produced (37.2×10^9 to $47.0 \times 10^9 \text{ m}^3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$) is put to reuse (Jones et al., 2021; Scanlon et al., 2023). Prominent differences exist in terms of WW collection, processing and utilization can be correlated with the level of economic development in different countries. Considering these factors, global WW production is estimated to reach 470 billion m^3 by the completion of this decade and further increase to 574 billion m^3 by 2050. WW production extrapolated from aggregation analysis for Asia; Africa (Sub-Saharan, Middle East and North); Europe, Latin America and the Caribbean, North America and Oceania, is estimated to be 360–380 billion m^3 annually (Jones et al., 2021; Qadir et al., 2020).

Table 1. Categories of wastewater generated as sources of contaminants and their effects

Category of WW generation	Source	Examples	Effects	References
Agricultural	Nutrients	N, P, K from fertilizers, animal excreta, ammonia	Eutrophication and algal blooms	(Chahal et al., 2016; Mateo-Sagasta et al., 2015)
	Pesticides	Carbamates, DDT, organochlorides, Herbicides	Pesticide toxicity which leads to nausea, irritation in the eye. A few are carcinogenic	(Mateo-Sagasta et al., 2015)
	Pathogens	<i>E. coli</i> , coccus and coliforms	Diseases such as gastroenteritis, typhoid etc	(Chahal et al., 2016; Mateo-Sagasta et al., 2015)
Industrial	Disinfection byproducts (DBPs)*	Trihalomethanes and acetic acids	Carcinogenic and mutagenic effects	(Hu et al., 2020; Srivastav and Kaur, 2020)
	Pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs)*	1,2-dioxane, hydroquinone and metals, codeine, caffeine, ibuprofen	Cytopathological, reproductive and physiological disorders in aquatic environments. Mutagenic and genotoxic effect	(Lavilla et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020)
	Paper, pulp and leather manufacturing	Phenols, resins, abietic acid	Increases N P K content of the soil. Phytotoxicity and aquatic toxicity	(Vysokomornaya et al., 2015a)
	Nuclear and thermal power plants	Petroleum, vanadium salt, Hydrazine, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole	Decrease in DO and rise in pH. Eutrophication, Malnutrition in fishes	(Vysokomornaya et al., 2015b)
	Textile processing	Formaldehydes, pentachlorophenol, Cd, Pb, surfactants, dyes	Carcinogenic, Abnormality in reproduction, skin irritation and respiratory diseases	(Khan and Malik, 2014; Kishor et al., 2021)
	Pharmaceuticals	Antibiotics (Enoxacin, Ciprofloxacin), antihistamines (Cetirizine)	Increase in antibiotic resistance, Endocrine disruption, Development of antibiotic-resistance bacteria	(Fick et al., 2009; Khan and Malik, 2014)
	Electroplating industries	Heavy metals such as Cd, Zn, Ca	Bioaccumulation, toxic and carcinogenic even at low concentration. Zn poisoning and Hg poisoning	(Vysokomornaya et al., 2015a; Zhang et al., 2023)
	Petrochemical refineries and petrochemical plants (PRPP)	Acetone, petroleum products, phenol	Inhibit entry of sunlight therefore affecting aquatic flora and fauna. Have genotoxic and carcinogenic effect	(Vysokomornaya et al., 2015a)
Domestic	Graywater	Kitchen, bathroom, laundry	Plant toxicity. Microbiological risk due to presence of pathogens	(Abbas et al., 2022; Khajvand et al., 2022)
	Blackwater	Urine and feces	Increases urea and ammonia content	(Abbas et al., 2022)

Globally, Asia has the highest annual approximates of 159 billion m³, or 42% of the world's total urban WW. In terms of per capita metrics, North America produces the highest volume of wastewater, 231 m³ (Figure 1), followed by Europe (Scanlon et al., 2023).

Surprisingly, the lowest (~50%) of the global average annual amount of wastewater per capita is generated by Sub-Saharan Africa (46 m³). This is explained by the insufficient supply of water and inadequate WW collection systems. In a study by Jones et al. (2021), WW production was correlated with economic discrepancies regardless of geographic location. The regression analysis in the same study presents i) population size, ii) average economic output per inhabitant, iii) level of access to WW services are critical to the amounts of WW generated per capita. Countries such as Niger, Burkina Faso and Ethiopia have wastewater production values in compliance with the minimum water requirements for survival recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2011), with values of 2.7, 3.4 and 4.2 m³ yr⁻¹ per capita, respectively. In contrast, the densely populated Asian countries and Pacific regions produce 117.6 × 10⁹ m³ yr⁻¹ wastewater. High-income countries, which constitute approximately 16% of the global population, produce approximately 42% of the global wastewater, whereas middle- and lower-income countries, which constitute ~50% of the global population, produce only ~20% of the global wastewater. In terms of individual nations, the top producers of wastewater are the United States (211 m³ yr⁻¹ per capita) and Canada (198 m³ yr⁻¹ per

capita), along with smaller European nations (such as Andorra, which produces 257 m³ yr⁻¹ per capita; Austria, which produces 220 m³ yr⁻¹ per capita; and Monaco, which produces 203 m³ yr⁻¹ per capita) (Scanlon et al., 2023). On the other hand, the majority of sub-Saharan African nations generate less than 10 m³ yr⁻¹ per person, well within the minimum water requirements for survival recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2011). Densely populated Asian countries and Pacific regions produce 117.6 × 10⁹ m³ yr⁻¹.

Fig. 1. The annual volume of wastewater (m³/capita/year) produced per capita in seven regions (Qadir et al., 2020)

The United Nations has estimated that approximately 80% of untreated sewage is dumped into water resources globally (UN Report 2017). These factors impact societal functioning, dent healthcare budgets and cause a loss of economic activity. Sustainability at the level of economic feasibility, social equity, infrastructural applicability, and environmental and ecosystem health provides opportunities for technological development and regulatory policies in the sanitation sector (Van Welie and Romijn, 2018). It is important to recognize WW generation and collection as separate processes, as all the produced WW that is collected may not be treated subsequently (Mateo-Sagasta et al., 2015). Owing to a lack of renewable water sources, WW collection is relatively high (74%) in the Middle East and North Africa region and noticeably low (58%) in East Asia and the Pacific. In Western Europe, the rates of WW collection and repurposing are the highest, at 88% and 86%, respectively. The lowest percentages of similar procedures are observed in sub-Saharan Africa (23%) and South Asia (31% and 16%) (Ehalt Macedo et al., 2022; Jones et al., 2021). To bridge the gap in WW generation and treatment, many countries have adopted policies in compliance with SDG 6 standards, as discussed below.

Policies for disposal and treatment

Waste management policies vary significantly across nations, and a brief discussion is presented here to illustrate their diversity. The Royal Commission on Sewage Disposal (1898--1915) in Britain was one of the first nations to introduce water risk management protocols and formulate BOD and TSS standards in treated WW at 20 and 30 mg/l, respectively. Most of the present-day standards and policies use this benchmark of assimilative capacity for end use of water until recently. As evident from Figure 2, of all the regulated parameters, BOD, TSS and COD are the most relevant determinants for setting standards across nations.

Fig. 2. National discharge standards of 100 countries (adapted from the WHO, 2018)

A challenge in setting up WW treatment and reuse standards is often the large geographic area, nonhomogeneous economies and social structure (Table 2). In the regulatory structure of the 1991 Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD), emphasis has been placed on the collection and treatment of wastewater, especially from more than the assemblage of 2,000 population equivalents (PEs), and includes water from surface runoff and household and manufacturing effluents. The member nations are mandated to regulate collection, ensure that industrial discharges reach treatment facilities, monitor effluent standards, implement nutrient removal objectives, track treatment facilities and manage the disposal of sewage sludge.

The Water Framework Directive (WFD) (European Commission, 2019), has emphasized consideration of water quality and the ecological conditions of surface and ground water resources for comparisons of healthy ecosystems. Ireland, through the Irish Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), issued specific domestic wastewater treatment systems (DWWTS) for PE \leq 10 (EPA, 2010). The EPA is developing technologies for septic tanks for initial treatment, wetland construction, soil filters and sand filters for secondary and tertiary treatment, and package plants (primary and secondary treatment). France has categorized standards for the low-capacity treatment plants according to daily BOD levels; below 1.2 kg of BOD per day and between 1.2 kg of BOD to 120 kg per day (Legifrance, 2007, 2009). Similar to Brazil, Tanzania has adopted participatory process at a national level which is reviewed every 5 years. Recent Indian standards planned by the NGT are the strongest guidelines for BOD, TSS, and TN removal, whereas Peru, Romania and Tanzania have moderate levels of regulation (Table 2) (TBS 2015, NGT 2019). On the other hand, Ecuador and Jordan have less stringent limits (EEA 2017a, b and c). The USEPA (2012) has strict discharge standards as well as recommendations for treatment technologies. The Horizon 2020 EU-funded project INNOQUA has been resolved to reduce the generation of sludge and limit emissions in terms of wastewater flow, therefore offering a natural solution to home wastewater problems (Tompkins et al., 2019). It aims to create a treatment system that is both economical and effective to minimize the global discharge of untreated WW as well as encourage reuse of the treated WW, primarily for irrigation and agriculture (Clifford et al., 2023).

The inclusion of the economic, social, health and environmental benefits of adequate sanitation by policymakers is integral to support the rapid growth of South East Asia (SEA) economies (da Conceição Rebelo, 2024; Sijm-Eeken et al., 2023). According to World Bank Water and Sanitation Program reports, a lack of adequate sanitation facilities has weakened the annual income of Cambodia, Lao People's Democratic Republic and Vietnam, in addition to direct health impacts, high access costs for clean drinking water, and tourism losses. The UN has emphasized decentralized wastewater treatment systems (DEWATS) for the SEA region and other parts of the globe. For the accomplishment of Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDG6), the policy guiding manual of ESCAP, UN-Habitat and AIT (2015) has recommended that both national and local SEA policy makers and experts develop pro-poor policies and sustainable sanitation services; advocate for DEWATS in peri-urban and secondary cities; and resolve sanitation reforms (Obaideen et al., 2022).

Intentional treated-WW reuse depends on the availability of resources required for its treatment, which are expected to be available fairly in high-revenue countries. Almost half (52%) of the intentionally treated-WW which is intentionally reused, has been observed in high-income countries, and approximately 37% has been reported in upper-middle-income countries. The treated-WW which intentionally reused is greater in the upper- to middle-income (25%) and lower- to middle-income groups (25%) than in the high-income group (19%) (Global Wastewater Status, unu.edu).

Treatment strategies

Levels of wastewater treatment

There are several sources of wastewater generation, and appropriate treatment of WW is dependent on its level of contamination (Nishat et al., 2023). The treatment of WW is categorized into three levels: primary, secondary and tertiary (Figure 3) (Krishnan et al., 2023). Many municipal corporations use wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in different countries to make WW suitable for reuse. The WW treatment system is designed to reduce the biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and to remove nutrients, microbes, suspended solids, microplastics and toxic products (Ahmed et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2023). Anthropogenic waste includes large amounts of solid materials such as cans and plastics, which are non-biodegradable (Loh et al., 2022; Thacharodi et al., 2023).

Table 2. Comparison of WW discharge and reuse standards in a few representatives. Additional regulations exist for heavy metals, sulphates, nitrates spores, and phages.

Country	Discharge Standards										Wastewater reuse standards					
	PE treated	pH	Temperature (°C)	SS (mg SS/l)	COD (mg COD/l)	BOD (mg BOD/l)	TN (mg N/L)	TP (mg P/l)	Microbial indicators	BOD	COD	TN	Coliforms	TSS	pH	Helminth eggs (HE)/Intestinal Nematodes (IN)
EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD)	>2,000			35/90% reduction	125/75% reduction	25/70-90% reduction	-	-		A. All irrigation methods <10 B. All irrigation methods 25 C. Drip irrigation 25	mg/l	mg/l	CFU/100ml	mg/l	-	egg/l or applicable <1 HE and <<1,000 CFU/l <i>Legionella</i> spp.
France	<20			30		35	10	1					<100 or ND <i>E. coli</i>	<15		
Ecuador	20-2000	6-8.5	<25	50% reduction	60% reduction	35, 60% reduction				Varies			<10000	varies		
Jordan		6-9	+3°	130	200	100	50 TKN	10	<2000 FC MPN/100 ml				1000FC (MPN)		6-9	absent
India NGT 2019		5.5-9		20 TSS	50	10	10	1	<1,000 <i>E. coli</i> MPN/100 ml Nematodes < 1	30	100	70	<1.1E. coli	15	6-9	<1 (HE)

PE: population equivalent; SS: suspended solids; COD: chemical oxygen demand; BOD: biological oxygen demand; TN: total nitrogen; TP: total phosphorus

i. Preliminary treatment

This is the first and foremost preparatory treatment step that is a prerequisite for the rest of the treatment process and involves large amounts of solid floating waste, including fecal material, plastic, rags, wood, and heavier grit particles (Deluise et al., 2005). Preliminary treatment is divided into the following steps: screening, grinding, grit removal, flotation, equalization, and flocculation (Englande et al., 2015). The screening step is performed with the help of bars that remove all large solid wastes that can obstruct the further path of the treatment plant. Grit removal is accomplished by slowing down the flow of water, which allows settlement of the grit particles at the bottom (He et al., 2022). The remaining steps aid in removing suspended solids for further purification steps.

ii. Primary Treatment

After preliminary weeding, the sludge moves to the next level, where sedimentation tanks allow settlement of solid waste particles on the basis of gravity (Guz et al., 2015). The sludge then passes through metal screens (a physical process), which filter small solid wastes. Further comminution is performed by grinding the sludge to break down large particles into small particles (Deluise et al., 2005). Some large treatment plants are also capable of removing floating waste or “scums”, including fat and grease (Schier et al., 2009). The primary treatment is effective in removing approximately half of the SS and about one third of the BOD from sewage (<https://www.yasa.ltd/post/primary-treatment-of-wastewater-how-does-it-work>).

iii. Secondary treatment

The previous two steps are based mainly on physical methods for the removal of contaminants. However, the secondary treatment step mainly focuses on biological steps involving the removal of N and P to prevent eutrophication. This is achieved by using denitrifying phosphorus removal filters, autotrophic denitrification and a microalgae biological treatment system (Schier et al., 2009; Sinthusith et al., 2015; Zhao et al., 2021). For the implementation of this step, the WWTP employs aerobic, anaerobic or anoxic treatment methods involving the use of different microbes. Conventional WWTPs commonly use activated sludge processes (ASPs) during secondary treatment (Hansen et al., 2007; Rout et al., 2021), which require decomposers to form activated sludge, and the tanks are aerated via an air-bubbling system. As decomposers and detritus feeders readily feed on this nutrient-rich medium in the presence of oxygen, frequent aeration helps to dissolve the generated oxygen allowing the utilization of organic matter.

From an aeration tank, the water passes through a secondary clarifier tank (Gemza et al., 2022), where the flocks of microbes settle in still water; therefore, the water (without these microbes) flows on. Overall, secondary treatment enhances the aerobic oxidation of BOD, and the expected outcome of this step is the removal of more than 90% of pathogenic bacteria from sewage (Abdel-Raouf et al., 2012).

iv. Tertiary Treatment

Secondary treatment is effective in removing the majority of pathogenic bacteria, but the treated water is still not ready for irrigation and drinking because of the presence of micropollutants. These organic micropollutants (OMPs) can include remaining microbes, antibiotics, microplastics, pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs), steroid hormones, industrial chemicals, pesticides, etc. (Choi et al., 2022). Hence, at this step, chemical treatment is used to disinfect the water. The most widely used disinfectant is chlorine (Burch et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020), but chlorine alone may cause harm and is often used with sodium hypochlorite for safer use.

Therefore, the latest WWTPs employ disinfectants such as ozone gas, UV light and chlorination to make the water ready for use (González et al., 2023). Ozone gas shows promising results in killing microbes and improving water quality by breaking down oxygen gas, but at the same time, it is explosive and energy exhaustive (Molinos-Senante et al., 2013; Pistocchi et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2021). UV treatment is far safer at killing resistant microbes (Zhao et al., 2021) but does not improve water quality. Some OMPs can be a matter of concern and therefore require adsorption with powdered activated carbon (PAC) and biological activated carbon (BAC) processes (Choi et al., 2022).

Throughout these steps, the BOD level is expected to decrease from 200 ppm (incoming sewage) to 20–20 ppm after final treatment; thus, the treated wastewater can now be discharged from other water bodies for further use.

Fig. 3. Modules in a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP)

Biological alternatives for wastewater treatment

Biological treatments for wastewater aim for environmentally friendly transformation and removal of pollutants to yield reusable water. Chemical and physical treatment methods for wastewater treatment have been attempted at various levels and are a major challenge for any country. Hence, worldwide emphasis has been placed on developing eco-friendly and economical alternatives (Vieira et al., 2022). In this section, a brief synopsis of bioremediation and phytoremediation, which involves various techniques, such as activated sludge, oxidative ponds, trickling filters, biofilters and biofilms, and bioreactors, is presented, along with other innovative approaches (Babu Ponnusami et al., 2023; Bibi et al., 2023).

i. Phytoremediation

Phytoremediation applies to plants, plant-origin microbes or plant-associated microbiota agents to decontaminate and degrade pollutants from soil or water. Several plant species can amass, degrade contaminants and stimulate the ecosystem to restore its health (Meagher, 2000; Oh et al., 2014).

Fig. 4. Phytoremediation: an overview. (Adapted from Kafle et al., 2022)

The desirable traits for the selection of plant species to survive under adverse conditions of toxic HMs and pollutants include low maintenance, a high biomass-producing, dense root system, high absorption capacity, and herbivory resistance, in addition to easy cultivation (Akpore et al., 2014; Mustafa and Hayder, 2021; Shabani and Sayadi, 2012). Figure 4 shows adaptations of phytoremediation for degradation (rhizodegradation, phytodegradation), accumulation (phytoextraction, rhizofiltration), dissipation (phytovolatilization), and immobilization (hydraulic control and phytostabilization) to vitiate, eliminate, or immobilize pollutants. Rhizofiltration, phytodegradation or rhizodegradation are the most common methods used for the treatment of wastewater. A list of various plant species commonly used for phytoremediation is presented in Table 3 (Ekperusi et al., 2019).

The water hyacinth, or *Eichhornia crassipes*, has gained special attention for treatment purposes because of its rapid proliferation, high yield, and high pollutant absorption properties (Balali-Mood et al., 2021). Successful remediation of Cd- and Hg-polluted water by water hyacinth is an example (Wang et al., 2020). Reports have cited effective outcomes by the application of *Azolla pinnata*, the aquatic fern to treat diluted dairy wastewater, degradation of organic pollutants rich WW from industry by *Alisma lanceolatum*, *Carex cuprina*, *Epilobium hirsutum* and *Juncus inflexus* (Chandanshive et al., 2017; Guitonny-Philippe et al., 2015). The salt marsh halophyte *Halimione portulacoides* efficiently converts highly toxic Cr (VI) into mildly toxic Cr (III) (Duarte et al., 2024).

Textile industry waste dumped into water introduces harmful chemicals, and colored dyes may inhibit light penetration, hindering aquatic ecosystems. For this purpose, several ferns and other plant species, including *Aster amellus*, *Glandularia pulchella*, and *Zinnia angustifolia*, have been confirmed to degrade dyes, such as Acid Orange 7 and Basic Red 46 (Khandare and Govindwar, 2015).

Table 3. Selected common plant species used for phytoremediation of wastewater

Type of plant	Plant species	Use	References
Free-floating	<i>Azolla pinnata</i>	Treat dairy wastewater	(Goala et al., 2021)
	<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> , <i>Pistia stratiotes</i> , <i>Marsilea mutica</i>	Heavy metal absorption	(Flomo and Chaki, 2024)
	<i>Salvinia molesta</i>	Reduce phosphorus	(Kumar and Deswal, 2020)
	<i>Lemna</i> spp, <i>Spirodela polyrhiza</i>	Absorption of Uranium and Arsenic	(Mkandawire et al., 2004)
Submerged	<i>Najas indica</i>	Lead bioaccumulation	(Singh et al., 2010)
	<i>Ruppia maritima</i> , <i>Zannichellia palustris</i>	Boron removal	(Parnian et al., 2016)
	<i>Hydrilla verticillata</i> , <i>Vallisneria americana</i>	Removal of heavy metals	(Yuan et al., 2022)
	<i>Egeria densa</i>	Phytoremediation of saflufenacil	(Alonso et al., 2021)
Emergent	<i>Distichlis spicata</i>	Arsenic remediation	(Pratas et al., 2005)
	<i>Cyperus</i> spp	Hydrocarbon phytoremediation	(Escalante-Espinosa et al., 2005)
	<i>Imperata cylindrical</i> , <i>Iris virginica</i> , <i>Nuphar lutea</i>	Heavy metal phytoremediation	(Naing et al., 2023)
Terrestrial	<i>Brassica juncea</i>	Lead and cadmium phytoremediation	(Goswami and Das, 2015)
	<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Nickel and lead phytoremediation	(Mukhtar et al., 2010)

Often, aids and augmentants such as biochar, compost waste and other natural organics (Paz-Ferreiro et al., 2013), chelating chemicals such as EDTA (Shahid et al., 2014), microbial and fungal amendments (Afzal et al., 2014) or transgenic plants (Abhilash et al., 2009; Kawahigashi, 2009) are used to enhance phytoremediation. These agents work by decreasing toxicity and increasing availability or generally support plant growth.

Thus, phytoremediation via the use of resilient plant species is a promising solution for the removal of toxic contaminants and recovery of nutrients from WW. In addition to providing natural, renewable and environmentally friendly alternatives, the secondary waste generated via this method has a low carbon footprint and can be used as feedstock for other applications. The technology, however, has a few concerns and scope for improvement, with the most serious concern of entry and bioaccumulation of contaminants in the food chain. It is also limited to the treatment of shallow water bodies and is a slow process overall (Mustafa and Hayder, 2021).

ii. Bioremediation using microbes

The expanding population and increasing human dependence on industrial products have resulted in increased water usage and hence water generation as waste (Bilal and Iqbal, 2020; Da Silva Vilar et al., 2021). Use of microbes for bioremediation of such polluted water depends on the specific conditions like nutrients, oxygen and pH. A variety of biological treatment techniques are available that involve direct (bacteria, fungi, algae and phytoremediation) or derived applications of microbes (activated sludge and biofilms) (Figure 5). Among these bacteria, bacteria are the most favored

owing to their ease of cultivation, rapid proliferation and diverse potential to remediate organic contaminants (Bhatia et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2017). A more potent approach is the addition of a microbial consortium that combines the degradative properties of different microbes, which can be adaptive and effective for a variety of conditions and pollutants. The outcomes of such conversions are minerals and metabolites that are used for cellular growth and metabolism. In addition to being an economic option, the use of microbes has the advantages of providing a high surface-area to volume ratio for effective bioconversion (Hassaan and El Nemr, 2017).

Fig. 5. Bioremediation of wastewater. The choice of bacteria-based bioremediation method depends on the type and the level of contaminant as well as ecological interactions. (Haripriyan et al., 2022; Saeed et al., 2022; Singha et al., 2023)

The cyanobacteria *Aphanocapsu* sp. and *Plectonema* sp. have been reported to treat phenols, amines, and aliphatic aldehydes present in crude oil. Anaerobic bacteria have been successfully applied in sewage treatments with a combination of sulfate-reducing bacteria such as the *Desulfovibrio*, *Desulfotomaculum*, *Desulfobacter*, and *Desulfococcus* genera (El Houari et al., 2020). Degradation of pesticides and hydrocarbons is reported by the application of *Pseudomonas putida* (chlorobenzene (Kunze et al., 2009)), *Mycobacterium gilvum* (pyrene, benzo(a)pyrene; (Toyama et al., 2011), *Dechloromonas* sp. (benzene, toluene, xylene; (Chakraborty et al., 2005), *Bacillus pumilus* with *Microbacterium arborescens* (azo-dye derivatives, (Shehzadi et al., 2014) and *Sphingomonas* (HCH; (Garg et al., 2016). Anaerobic bacterial enzymes have been more successful against polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), trichloroethylene (TCE), and chloroform (Karigar and Rao, 2011).

Synthetic textile dyes offer a variety of color spectra with enhanced absorption and solubility (Chen et al., 2021). WW from the textile dyeing industry is dominated by azo dyes and additives (both inorganic and organic) (Wuhrmann et al., 1980). The general mechanism involved in the bacterial degradation of such wastewater involves enzymatic degradation involving laccase and azoreductase. A few dye-derivative examples include Red HE78 (*Bacillus* sp., (Zhang et al., 2018), methyl orange [*Aeromonas* sp. (Guibaud et al., 2006)], xylydine ponceau 2 R (*Shewanella marisflavi*, (Zhuang et al., 2015), Congo Red [*Pseudomonas extremorientalis*, (Šoštarić et al., 2018)], and Direct Black G [*Anoxybacillus* sp. (Pandey et al., 2014)]. The critical determinants for the degradation of petroleum hydrocarbons (resins, asphaltenes, aromatics, and saturates) by microbes range from temperature and inorganic nutrients to the variety of hydrocarbons present (Varjani and Upasani, 2017). Numerous aerobic bacteria have evolved degradation pathways involving oxygenases, peroxidases, and hydroxylases to degrade a variety of petroleum wastes (Table 4). Sulfur-oxidizing bacteria (SOB) and Sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB) have been engineered to bioremediate and recover anions such as SO₄²⁻ from wastewater (Wu et al., 2021). Their application in an anaerobic sequencing batch biofilm reactor (ASBBR) containing mineral coal resulted in the removal of more than 50% of SO₄²⁻ and organic matter (Bagheri Novair et al., 2024). Efforts have been made to apply genetically engineered microalgae in wastewater treatment and carbon fixation systems. Manipulations for gene integration and expression, gene editing via CRISPR and ZFNs, and RNAi have been successfully tested for *Chlamydomonas*, *Volvox*, *Gonium*, *Monoraphidium*, etc. (Kuo et al., 2022). Recent advances in the integration of omics analysis with metabolic engineering can harness the true potential of bioremediation. For example, omics analysis revealed a direct correlation between nitrogen starvation induced by C/N ratio manipulation yielding an enhanced lipid component of microalgae, helpful for optimizing the biomass concentration (Naseema Rasheed et al., 2023). Microorganism-assisted synthesis of nanomaterials is emerging as an environmentally

beneficial and cost-effective approach. Studies have shown that *Chlorella vulgaris*-derived nanocomposite particles of exopolysaccharides and iron oxide remove PO_4^{3-} and NH_4^+ in wastewater treatment plants (Govarthanan et al., 2020).

Table 4. Microbes for the degradation of petrochemicals (Adapted from Amran et al., 2021)

Gaseous hydrocarbons degrading bacteria		
<i>Pseudomonas</i>	<i>Corynebacterium</i>	<i>Mycobacterium</i>
<i>Arthrobacter</i>	<i>Brevibacterium</i>	<i>Nocardia</i>
Oil-degrading bacteria		
<i>Oleiphilus</i>	<i>Cycloclasticus</i>	<i>Alcanivorax</i>
<i>Neptunomonas</i>	<i>Marinobacter</i>	
Hydrocarbons degrading bacteria efficient in seawater and soil		
<i>Acinetobacter</i>	<i>Achromobacter</i>	<i>Arthrobacter</i>
<i>Mycobacterium</i>	<i>Brevibacterium</i>	<i>Nocardia</i>
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Flavobacteria</i>	<i>Corynebacterium</i>
<i>Pseudomonas</i>	<i>Sphingomonas</i>	<i>Gordonia</i>
Biosurfactant producing bacteria		
<i>Pseudomonas</i> (Rhamnolipids)	<i>Aeromonas</i> (Glycolipid)	<i>Bacillus</i> (Surfactin)
<i>Candida bombicola</i> (Soporolipids)	<i>Candida tropicalis</i> (Lipomannan)	

iii. Plant based natural coagulants

Hydrophobic colloids are the liquid-phase homogenous or heterogeneous mixtures which are dispersed in the WW with generally a negative adsorbed charge to maintain stasis in the liquid phase. These are removed via coagulation by inducing physical re-associations and chemical re-arrangements to form large aggregates which are then filtered, sedimented or centrifuged. For treatment purposes, natural plant-based coagulants are regaining popularity over the inorganic and synthetic organic polymers owing to their ancient use, local availability, renewable generation and degradation, non-hazardous impact on environment and health as well low-cost production and downstream process management. Studies have shown plant seed extracts (*Moringa oleifera* seeds) and bark resins (Benalia et al., 2024) to be more effective and safer alternative to most widely used chemical alternative, alum. For treatment purposes, only cationic polyelectrolytes are useful as these destabilize the colloidal particles by producing cationic species and promoting coagulation. Several studies have reported treatment of WW effluents from the industrial for dairy products (*Moringa oleifera*), palm oil mining (*Moringa oleifera*, *Cassia obtusifolia* and rice starch), coffee pulping and fermentation (*Moringa oleifera*), cassava processing (*Abelmoschus esculentus*, *Ficus exasperata* and *Bridelia ferrugeneae*), breweries (vegetable tannin) and slaughter house (*Moringa oleifera*) (Azmi et al., 2023; Balbinoti et al., 2023; Bialeski et al., 2024; Garde et al., 2017; Hasan et al., 2024; Heidari and Kordbacheh, 2023; Teles et al., 2024). Apart from moringa seeds, mango (seed), cactus (pad) and okra (seed pods) have shown potential for turbidity reducing abilities (Othmani et al., 2020).

Despite the benefits and successful application, commercialization of plant-based coagulants is hindered because several reasons including insufficient plantations and variations in seasonal varieties of the raw material; limited consumer awareness; technological gaps in economically viable extraction and application methodology; and non-standardized norms for production processes and quality check for herbal extracts (Balbinoti et al., 2023).

Innovative initiatives

i. Biochar

Among the various sustainable methods for reducing carbon, biochar has emerged as a biological alternative for reducing carbon footprint (Regkouzas et al., 2025; Woolf et al., 2010). To define, biochar is the result of the thermochemical conversion of plant products or other carbonaceous materials (Figure 6) at very high temperatures by excluding oxygen (Beesley et al., 2011). The process is called pyrolysis, which under high-temperature and reducing environments, generates bio-oil, syngas, and biochar through the carbonization of biomass (Jayakumar et al., 2021). Although biochar is used for a variety of purposes, including C sequestration, greenhouse gas emission reduction, land remediation, and soil fertilization, in WWTPs, it is used as a sorbent or for contaminant immobilization (Rajapaksha et al., 2016). Biochars are further modified on the basis of the contaminant types and remediation goals. These modifications include acid treatment, base treatment, surfactant modification, amination, impregnation of mineral sorbents, steam activation, magnetic modification, and engineering of biologically enhanced biochar (Jayakumar et al., 2021; Rajapaksha et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2021).

Figure 6. Production and application of biochar in treatment of WW generated from industry, agriculture and municipal activities.

For WW treatment plants, biochar has gained importance because of the following benefits: 1) it is economical even for low-income communities; 2) it is renewable; 3) it is able to remove biological, chemical and physical contaminants effectively; and 4) unlike chlorine, it does not change the organoleptic properties of water (Gwenzi et al., 2017). However, its efficiency largely depends upon the method and source of production; hence, a better formulation can result in better sorbent properties and, in turn, better purification of water. Some of the commonly used biochars used in wastewater treatment are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Various sources of biomass feedstock used for the production of biochar

Type of contaminant	Biomass feedstock	Production method (P=Pyrolysis)	Target contaminant	Capacity (mg/g) (or) removal efficiency (%)	Reference
Heavy metals	Bamboo, bagasse, hickory wood, peanut hull	P	Cd, Pb & Cu	14.3 mg/g for Pb ²⁺	(Zhou et al., 2017)
	Orange peel	P	Cu and Pb	85% and 94%	(Afolabi and Musonge, 2023)
	Corn stalks	P	Pb	97.50%	(Yang et al., 2018)
	Sewage sludge	P	Pb	100%	(Ifthikar et al., 2017)
	Coconut shell, dried neem seeds	P	Cr	99.90%	(Vidya Vijay et al., 2019)
	Pinewood	P	Cr	99.60%	(Sforza et al., 2020)
	Tobacco petiole	P	Cr	66.70%	(Zhou et al., 2017)
	Corn straw	P	Cr	90%	(Zhao et al., 2021)
	Oil palm fiber	P	As	61%	(Qiao et al., 2018)
	Rice straw	P	As	85%	(J et al., 2018)
	<i>Sacchararum ravannae</i>	P	As	72.10%	(Saikia et al., 2010)
	Tetra Paks	P	As	95%	(Ding et al., 2018)
	Malt spent rootlets	P	Hg(II)	103 mg/g	(Boutsika et al., 2014)
Dyes	Bamboo cane	Phosphoric acid modification then pyrolysis at 400, 500, and 600 °C	Lanasyn Orange and Lanasyn Gray	2.6 × 10 ³ mg/g for both dyes (Lanasyn Orange)	(Pradhananga et al., 2017)
	Pecan nutshell	P	Reactive Red 141	85	(Zarzycki et al., 2023)
	Switchgrass	P	Orange G	256 mg/g	(Park et al., 2019)

	Tapioca peel	P	Rhodamine B	66%	(Vigneshwaran et al., 2021)
	Date palm fronds	P	Methylene blue	210 mg/g	(Ghany, 2020)
Phenols and PAHs	Sewage sludge	P	Hydroquinone	83.56(Fe-GAC)	(Tyagi and Anand, 2023)
	Rice straw	P	PAHs	58.80%	(Zhang et al., 2018)
	Loofah sponges	P	PAHs	31.90%	(Zarzycki et al., 2023)
	Malt spent rootlets	P	Phenanthrene	23.5 mg/g	(Valili et al., 2013)
	Orange peel	P	Naphthalene and 1-naphthol	80.8 mg/g for naphthalene and 186.5 mg/g for 1-naphthol	
Pesticides	Maize straw and pig manure	P	Thiacloprid	87.75%	(Cai et al., 2022)
	Almond shell	P	Dibromochloro propane	102 mg/g	(Klasson et al., 2013)
	Broiler litter	P	Deisopropylatrazine	Approximately 83.3 mg/g for BL700 with steam activation	(Islam et al., 2021)
	Soybean crops	Carboxylation and O-methylation of 2,5-dichlorophenol	Dicamba	237.384 mg/g	(Wilson et al., 2022)
	Cotton crops	Reaction of Isopropylamine with cyanuric acid at temperatures between 18-32 °C	Atrazine	0.5 mg/g	(Mehta et al., 2024)
	Maple, elm and oak woodchips and barks	P	Atrazine and simazine	451–1,158 mg/g for atrazine and 243–1,066 mg g ⁻¹ for simazine	(Zheng et al., 2010)
Antibiotics	Sawdust	ZnCl ₂ and FeCl ₃ 6H ₂ O solution doped at 100 °C then calcined at 600 °C for 2 h	Tetracycline	Above 89% after three cycles	(Zhou et al., 2017)
	Rice straw	P	Tetracycline	97%	(Fu et al., 2019)
	Maize straw	P	Oxytetracycline	63%	(Jia et al., 2013)
	Cassava waste	P	Norfloxacin	96.20%	(Luo et al., 2018)
	Wheat straw	P	Norfloxacin	88.10%	(Zhang et al., 2018)
	Yeast	P	Sulfamethoxazole	98.97%	(Peng et al., 2021)
	Bagasse	P	Sulfamethoxazole	83.30%	(Huang et al., 2020)
	Cotton straw	P	Sulfamethoxazole	71%	(Sun et al., 2018)
	Corn straw	P	Sulfadiazine	74%	(Sun et al., 2018)
	Wood	P	Thiamethoxan	22.80%	(You et al., 2020)
	Date stone	P	Ibuprofen	96.24%	(Chakraborty et al., 2020)
	Pig manure	P	Diclofenac	99.60%	(Lonappan et al., 2018)
Indicator organisms and pathogens	Rice husk	P	Fecal indicator bacteria	3.9 log units of bacteria removed	(Kaetzl et al., 2019)
	Avocado Seed, Avocado Peel, Grapefruit Peel, Brown Seaweed	Anaerobic Digestion	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	>1 log CFU/mL of removed bacteria	(Granados et al., 2022)
	Spent <i>E. coli</i> Media	Green Microalgae <i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	0.1051 Log CFU/mL of removed bacteria	(Zhang et al., 2017)
	Hardwood	P	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	>1 log ₁₀ CFU of bacteria removed	(Perez-Mercado et al., 2019)
	Wood chips	P steam activation	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	3.62 ± 0.27 log units of bacteria removed	(Mohanty et al., 2014)

ii. Use of computational methods in wastewater treatment

Another obstacle faced during the treatment process of WW is the optimization of energy efficiency. Therefore, effective machine learning and AI-based models are being developed to predict energy and economically efficient ways (Wang et al., 2023). These include deterministic, stochastic, and time series-based models. These models are used to predict or forecast the effluent parameters, influent flow, and detection of anomalies or faults during the WWT process and energy consumption optimization (Duarte et al., 2024). Thus, the use of such computational tools helps researchers understand the data and variables associated with wastewater treatment and the dynamic relationships among those variables. The predictive models help increase effluent without compromising water quality or reducing environmental risk. Some examples of predictive models include artificial neural networks (ANNs), support vector machines (SVMs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems (ANFISs), genetic algorithms (GA), and particle swarm optimization (PSO) (Liu et al., 2024; Olabi et al., 2023; Shirkoohi et al., 2022).

These models have been used to understand different challenges associated with WWT. For example, a hydraulic model was developed by Zhang et al. (2018) to predict overflow in rainy situations. Three RNN models, namely, Elman, NARX and LSTM, were used with precipitation and flow data as the input data (Cunha et al., 2023; Siegelmann et al., 1997). Different combinations of wastewater quality parameters, including temperature (T), total nitrogen (TN), total phosphorus (TP), and hydraulic retention time (HRT), serve as inputs for the artificial neural network (ANN) to evaluate the impact of each variable on the efficiency of removing BOD, total nitrogen (TN), total phosphorus (TP), and total suspended solids (TSS) (Khatri et al., 2023). Various ANN algorithms have been used to treat oxytetracycline, 2-chlorophenol, synthetic saline effluent, malachite green dye, COD (Basha et al., 2010), phenolic wastewater and various other contaminants (Shirkoohi et al., 2022). ANFIS has been used to simulate the influence of variables on turbidity removal for the treatment of graywater (Nasr et al., 2016) and for drug removal (Farzin et al., 2020).

Furthermore, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) has become an increasingly important tool for assessing wastewater pollutants and optimizing the WWT process (Jujavarapu et al., 2024). Mathematical models are applied to increase the efficiency of WWTPs (Ruiz et al., 2023). Although AI models are increasingly adopted across various scientific fields, ensuring the reliability of these models remains paramount, particularly given the constraints posed by limited data availability.

iii. Use of nanoparticles (NPs) in wastewater treatment

NPs are small particles of approximately 1-100 nm in size and are known to have important properties, such as high surface adherence, catalytic conversions, and potency (Joseph et al., 2023). These NPs have widespread applications in biology and medicine. Recently, they have been found to be very useful in WWT strategies (Saeed et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2019; Zahmatkesh et al., 2023). A wide array of nanoparticles, including zerovalent metal nanoparticles (such as nanoscale zerovalent iron), zinc nanoparticles (Zn NPs), iron nanoparticles (Fe NPs), silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs), metal oxide nanoparticles (MNPs), TiO₂ nanoparticles, carbon nanotubes (CNTs), and quantum dots (QDs), have proven effective in removing WW contaminants.

Challenges and Opportunities in the Treatment and Reuse of Wastewater

The challenges related to wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and the reuse of wastewater are subjected mainly to the geopolitical and socioeconomic characteristics of the respective regions or countries and include economic and environmental sustainability in terms of the consumption of energy and fossil fuels, operational costs, and management efficiency (Morris et al., 2021; Rosemarin et al., 2020). The greatest expense in running WWTPs is the consumption of energy. For instance, a decade back global energy requirement for WWTP was at 1395.6 TW-hours (Okan et al., 2023; Simon-Várhelyi et al., 2020). This amount is expected to double before 2040 (IEA, 2016), mainly due to an increase in the number of WWTPs. A major fraction of energy is utilized to power the machinery for aeration, pumping and sludge treatment. This consumption is estimated to reach ~314 TWh by 2040 for advanced WWTPs (Gallo et al., 2024). These high costs in the installation and implementation of treatment plants limit their inception in low-income communities despite their advantages (Silva, 2023; Yenkie, 2019).

In addition to substantial growth in the operational costs of different WWTPs, a dramatic upsurge in electricity consumption with considerable escalation in the emission of greenhouse gases (Yoshida, 1975) increases the carbon footprint with high operational costs, thereby making wastewater treatment highly unsustainable and unaffordable. Energy-efficient WWTPs and real-time process control are desirable to ensure the minimal consumption of energy with maximum

efficiency (Cardoso et al., 2021). One such initiative is TERI Advanced Oxidation Technology (TADOX®), which applies UV triggered photocatalysis for an advanced oxidation process (AOP) at the secondary treatment stage (<https://dst.gov.in/newly-advanced-oxidation-technology-can-enhance-waste-water-reuse-lower-cost>). Such technologies are expected to enhance WW reuse at a lower cost (Gandiglio et al., 2017).

In addition to energy consumption, operating costs are associated with a WWTP (Ćetković et al., 2022). These costs include expenditures for chemicals used to stabilize water quality; costs of repair and maintenance; personnel costs; and shadow costs for the non-removal of basic wastewater pollutants, such as N, P, and SSPs; and BOD and COD. Such integrations and quantifications are important for socio-adaptive technoeconomic evaluation and hence meaningful applications (Chen et al., 2021; Molinos-Senante et al., 2013). To facilitate this task, the life-cycle cost analysis (LCCA) method has been suggested by Rathore et al., (2022). The model considers capital investments and expenditures for operations, maintenance, repair, replacement, and disposal for estimating an optimum lowest life-cycle cost of a WWTP.

Another limitation is the failure of the optimum elimination of HMs, contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) and microbes by conventional WWTPs because of their small size and persistent nature (Matesun et al., 2024). Hence, efforts are being made to increase the removal of organic micropollutants (microbes, microplastics, pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs), pesticides, etc.) for efficient heavy metal detoxification, for which advanced physicochemical processes such as mechanical stress, UV light, ozone and advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) are adopted (Matesun et al., 2024; Qasem et al., 2021).

In addition to these limitations, societal acceptance also plays inhibitory roles in the use of treated water because of safety concerns and cleanliness (Hernández-Chover et al., 2023). An attempt to group the order of barriers as well as public acceptance of treated wastewater has been made via an economic analysis tool, PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal factors) (Gul et al., 2021; Morris et al., 2021) to integrate the impacts of socio-economic, geo-political, technological, environmental and legal considerations. Thus, initiatives, based on a sustainable circular economy, are required to overcome the challenges and barriers for the WW treatment and its repurposing processes (Baawain et al., 2020; Machineni, 2019; Meena et al., 2023).

Conclusion

Waste management policies differ worldwide, and effective policies need to be implemented to preserve and improve social health, environmental conservation, and the sustainability of water resources. This review highlights the importance of implementing stringent regulations and standards to govern wastewater treatment processes, as well as the need for continual monitoring and enforcement to ensure compliance with SDG 6 (UN). In addition to acts or regulations for enforcing the effective implementation of WWTPs, there is a critical need to implement innovative technologies and infrastructure upgrades to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of such plants. Promotion and prioritization of investments in technology development and infrastructure improvements will make WW a valuable resource for the future.

References

- Abbas MA, Iqbal M, Tauqeer HM, et al. (2022) Microcontaminants in wastewater. In: Environmental Micropollutants. Elsevier, pp. 315–329. Available at: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/B9780323905558000180> (accessed 24 August 2024).
- Abdel-Raouf N, Al-Homaidan AA and Ibraheem IBM (2012) Microalgae and wastewater treatment. Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences 19(3): 257–275.
- Abhilash PC, Jamil S and Singh N (2009) Transgenic plants for enhanced biodegradation and phytoremediation of organic xenobiotics. Biotechnology Advances 27(4): 474–488.
- Adjovu GE, Stephen H, James D, et al. (2023) Measurement of Total Dissolved Solids and Total Suspended Solids in Water Systems: A Review of the Issues, Conventional, and Remote Sensing Techniques. Remote Sensing 15(14): 3534.
- Aemig Q, Hélias A and Patureau D (2021) Impact assessment of a large panel of organic and inorganic micropollutants released by wastewater treatment plants at the scale of France. Water Research 188: 116524.

- Afolabi FO and Musonge P (2023) Synthesis, Characterization, and Biosorption of Cu²⁺ and Pb²⁺ Ions from an Aqueous Solution Using Biochar Derived from Orange Peels. *Molecules* 28(20): 7050.
- Afzal M, Khan QM and Sessitsch A (2014) Endophytic bacteria: Prospects and applications for the phytoremediation of organic pollutants. *Chemosphere* 117: 232–242.
- Ahmed J, Thakur A and Goyal A (2021) Industrial Wastewater and Its Toxic Effects. In: Shah MP (ed.) *Biological Treatment of Industrial Wastewater*. The Royal Society of Chemistry, pp. 1–14. Available at: <https://books.rsc.org/books/book/937/chapter/741366/Industrial-Wastewater-and-Its-Toxic-Effects> (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Ahmed M, Mavukkandy MO, Giwa A, et al. (2022) Recent developments in hazardous pollutants removal from wastewater and water reuse within a circular economy. *npj Clean Water* 5(1): 12.
- Akpor O, Otohinoyi D, Olaolu T, et al. (2014) POLLUTANTS IN WASTEWATER EFFLUENTS: IMPACTS AND REMEDIATION PROCESSES. *international journal of environmental research and earth science* 3: 50–59.
- Ali M, Wani SUD, Salahuddin M, et al. (2023) Recent advance of herbal medicines in cancer- a molecular approach. *Heliyon* 9(2): e13684.
- Alonso FG, Mielke KC, Brochado MG da S, et al. (2021) Potential of *Egeria densa* and *Pistia stratiotes* for the phytoremediation of water contaminated with saflufenacil. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health. Part. B, Pesticides, Food Contaminants, and Agricultural Wastes* 56(7): 644–649.
- Azmi LHM, Elaissari A, Fatehah MO, et al. (2023) Evaluation of Coagulation-Flocculation Treatment Technologies in Palm Oil Effluent Management. In: Wang LK, Wang M-HS, and Hung Y-T (eds) *Industrial Waste Engineering. Handbook of Environmental Engineering*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 509–551. Available at: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-031-46747-9_11 (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Baawain MS, Al-Mamun A, Omidvarborna H, et al. (2020) Public perceptions of reusing treated wastewater for urban and industrial applications: challenges and opportunities. *Environment, Development and Sustainability: A Multidisciplinary Approach to the Theory and Practice of Sustainable Development* 22(3). Springer: 1859–1871.
- Babu Ponnusami A, Sinha S, Ashokan H, et al. (2023) Advanced oxidation process (AOP) combined biological process for wastewater treatment: A review on advancements, feasibility and practicability of combined techniques. *Environmental Research* 237(Pt 1): 116944.
- Bagheri Novair S, Biglari Z, Asgari Lajayer B, et al. (2024) The role of sulphate-reducing bacteria (SRB) in bioremediation of sulphate-rich wastewater: Focus on the source of electron donors. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection* 184: 190–207.
- Balali-Mood M, Naseri K, Tahergorabi Z, et al. (2021) Toxic Mechanisms of Five Heavy Metals: Mercury, Lead, Chromium, Cadmium, and Arsenic. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 12: 643972.
- Balbinoti JR, Dos Santos Junior RE, De Sousa LBF, et al. (2023) Plant-based coagulants for food industry wastewater treatment. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 52: 103525.
- Basha CA, Soloman PA, Velan M, et al. (2010) Electrochemical degradation of specialty chemical industry effluent. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 176(1–3): 154–164.
- Beesley L, Moreno-Jiménez E, Gomez-Eyles JL, et al. (2011) A review of biochars' potential role in the remediation, revegetation and restoration of contaminated soils. *Environmental Pollution (Barking, Essex: 1987)* 159(12): 3269–3282.
- Benalia A, Derbal K, Amrouci Z, et al. (2024) Application of Plant-Based Coagulants and Their Mechanisms in Water Treatment: A Review. *Journal of Renewable Materials* 12(4): 667–698.
- Bhatia D, Sharma NR, Singh J, et al. (2017) Biological methods for textile dye removal from wastewater: A review. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology* 47(19): 1836–1876.
- Bialeski DD, Triques CC, Carvalho JK, et al. (2024) Natural Coagulant Functionalized with Magnetic Nanoparticles Better Treated Dairy Wastewater Compared to Bioremediation. *Waste and Biomass Valorization* 15(10): 6007–6019.

- Bibi A, Bibi S, Abu-Dieyeh M, et al. (2023) Towards sustainable physiochemical and biological techniques for the remediation of phenol from wastewater: A review on current applications and removal mechanisms. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 417: 137810.
- Bilal M and Iqbal HMN (2020) Microbial bioremediation as a robust process to mitigate pollutants of environmental concern. *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering* 2: 100011.
- Boutsika LG, Karapanagioti HK and Manariotis ID (2014) Aqueous Mercury Sorption by Biochar from Malt Spent Rootlets. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution* 225(1): 1805.
- Burch KD, Han B, Pichtel J, et al. (2019) Removal efficiency of commonly prescribed antibiotics via tertiary wastewater treatment. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research International* 26(7): 6301–6310.
- Butler BA and Ford RG (2018) Evaluating relationships between total dissolved solids (TDS) and total suspended solids (TSS) in a mining-influenced watershed. *Mine Water and the Environment* 37(1): 18–30.
- Cai X-Y, Xu M, Zhu Y-X, et al. (2022) Removal of Dinotefuran, Thiacloprid, and Imidaclothiz Neonicotinoids in Water Using a Novel *Pseudomonas monteilii* FCo2–Duckweed (*Lemna aquinoctialis*) Partnership. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 13: 906026.
- Canella Vieira C, Jarquin D, Do Nascimento EF, et al. (2022) Identification of genomic regions associated with soybean responses to off-target dicamba exposure. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 13: 1090072.
- Cardoso BJ, Rodrigues E, Gaspar AR, et al. (2021) Energy performance factors in wastewater treatment plants: A review. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 1 November 2021, p. 129107. Available at: <https://estudogeral.uc.pt/handle/10316/95863> (accessed 24 August 2024).
- Ćetković J, Knežević M, Lakić S, et al. (2022) Financial and Economic Investment Evaluation of Wastewater Treatment Plant. *Water* 14(1): 122.
- Chahal C, van den Akker B, Young F, et al. (2016) Pathogen and Particle Associations in Wastewater: Significance and Implications for Treatment and Disinfection Processes. *Advances in Applied Microbiology* 97: 63–119.
- Chakraborty P, Singh S, Gorai I, et al. (2020) Explication of physically and chemically treated date stone biochar for sorptive removal of ibuprofen from aqueous solution. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 33: 101022.
- Chakraborty R, O'Connor SM, Chan E, et al. (2005) Anaerobic Degradation of Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene, and Xylene Compounds by *Dechloromonas* Strain RCB. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 71(12): 8649–8655.
- Chandanshive VV, Rane NR, Tamboli AS, et al. (2017) Co-plantation of aquatic macrophytes *Typha angustifolia* and *Paspalum scrobiculatum* for effective treatment of textile industry effluent. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 338: 47–56.
- Chen G, An X, Li H, et al. (2021) Detoxification of azo dye Direct Black G by thermophilic *Anoxybacillus* sp. PDR2 and its application potential in bioremediation. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 214: 112084.
- Choi S, Yoom H, Son H, et al. (2022) Removal efficiency of organic micropollutants in successive wastewater treatment steps in a full-scale wastewater treatment plant: Bench-scale application of tertiary treatment processes to improve removal of organic micropollutants persisting after secondary treatment. *Chemosphere* 288(Pt 3): 132629.
- Clifford E, Dussaussois J-B, Schellenberg T, et al. (2023) Research Networks and Novel Partnerships for Sustainable Development – How an EU Research Project on Innovative Wastewater Technology Developed to an International Network for Nature-Based Solutions. In: Ittekkot V and Baweja JK (eds) *Science, Technology and Innovation Diplomacy in Developing Countries*. Research for Development. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, pp. 337–349. Available at: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-981-19-6802-0_22 (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Cunha B, Droz C, Zine A, et al. (2023) A Review of Machine Learning Methods Applied to Structural Dynamics and Vibroacoustic. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 200: 110535.
- da Conceição Rebelo MS (2024) Mozambique public investment in the water and sanitation sector and the targets of SDG6. *UCL open. Environment* 6: e067.

- Da Silva Vilar D, Torres NH, Bharagava RN, et al. (2021) Emerging contaminants in environment: occurrence, toxicity, and management strategies with emphasis on microbial remediation and advanced oxidation processes. In: *Microbe Mediated Remediation of Environmental Contaminants*. Elsevier, pp. 1–14. Available at: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/B9780128211991000018> (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Delanka-Pedige HMK, Munasinghe-Arachchige SP, Abeysiriwardana-Arachchige ISA, et al. (2021) Wastewater infrastructure for sustainable cities: assessment based on UN sustainable development goals (SDGs). *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology* 28(3): 203–209.
- Deluise F, Wang LK, Chang S-Y, et al. (2005) Screening and Comminution. In: Wang LK, Hung Y-T, and Shammas NK (eds) *Physicochemical Treatment Processes*. Totowa, NJ: Humana Press, pp. 1–19. Available at: <http://link.springer.com/10.1385/1-59259-820-x:001> (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Dey J and Vijay R (2021) A critical and intensive review on assessment of water quality parameters through geospatial techniques. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research International* 28(31): 41612–41626.
- Ding Z, Xu X, Phan T, et al. (2018) High adsorption performance for As(III) and As(V) onto novel aluminum-enriched biochar derived from abandoned Tetra Paks. *Chemosphere* 208: 800–807.
- Duarte MS, Martins G, Oliveira P, et al. (2024) A Review of Computational Modeling in Wastewater Treatment Processes. *ACS ES&T water* 4(3): 784–804.
- Ehalt Macedo H, Lehner B, Nicell J, et al. (2022) Distribution and characteristics of wastewater treatment plants within the global river network. *Earth System Science Data* 14(2): 559–577.
- Ekperusi AO, Sikoki FD and Nwachukwu EO (2019) Application of common duckweed (*Lemna minor*) in phytoremediation of chemicals in the environment: State and future perspective. *Chemosphere* 223: 285–309.
- El Houari A, Ranchou-Peyruse M, Ranchou-Peyruse A, et al. (2020) Microbial Communities and Sulfate-Reducing Microorganisms Abundance and Diversity in Municipal Anaerobic Sewage Sludge Digesters from a Wastewater Treatment Plant (Marrakech, Morocco). *Processes* 8(10): 1284.
- Englande AJ, Krenkel P and Shamas J (2015) Wastewater Treatment & Water Reclamation☆. In: *Reference Module in Earth Systems and Environmental Sciences*. Elsevier, p. B9780124095489095087. Available at: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/B9780124095489095087> (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Escalante-Espinosa E, Gallegos-Martínez ME, Favela-Torres E, et al. (2005) Improvement of the hydrocarbon phytoremediation rate by *Cyperus laxus* Lam. inoculated with a microbial consortium in a model system. *Chemosphere* 59(3): 405–413.
- Farzin S, Nabizadeh Chianeh F, Valikhan Anaraki M, et al. (2020) Introducing a framework for modeling of drug electrochemical removal from wastewater based on data mining algorithms, scatter interpolation method, and multi criteria decision analysis (DID). *Journal of Cleaner Production* 266: 122075.
- Fick J, Söderström H, Lindberg RH, et al. (2009) Contamination of surface, ground, and drinking water from pharmaceutical production. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 28(12): 2522–2527.
- Flomo M and Chaki S (2024) Phytoremediation, Effective Technology in the Removal of Nutrients and Heavy Metals in Wastewater by Slavonia Molesta, and Pistoia Stratiotes. *International Journal of Darshan Institute on Engineering Research & Emerging Technology* Vol. 12, No. 2, 2023: 13–20.
- Fu L, Liu Y, Wang Z, et al. (2019) Ion Adsorption of Rice Straw to Marine Heavy Metal Polluted Waste Water. *Journal of Coastal Research* 83(sp1): 359.
- Fukunaka A, Shimura M, Ichinose T, et al. (2023) Zinc and iron dynamics in human islet amyloid polypeptide-induced diabetes mouse model. *Scientific Reports* 13(1): 3484.
- Gallo M, Malluta D, Del Borghi A, et al. (2024) A Critical Review on Methodologies for the Energy Benchmarking of Wastewater Treatment Plants. *Sustainability* 16(5): 1922.
- Gandiglio M, Lanzini A, Soto A, et al. (2017) Enhancing the Energy Efficiency of Wastewater Treatment Plants through Co-digestion and Fuel Cell Systems. *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 5. *Frontiers*.

- Garde WK, Buchberger SG, Wendell D, et al. (2017) Application of Moringa Oleifera seed extract to treat coffee fermentation wastewater. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 329: 102–109.
- Garg N, Lata P, Jit S, et al. (2016) Laboratory and field scale bioremediation of hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH) contaminated soils by means of bioaugmentation and biostimulation. *Biodegradation* 27(2–3): 179–193.
- Gemza N, Janiak K, Zięba B, et al. (2022) Long-term effects of hydrocyclone operation on activated sludge morphology and full-scale secondary settling tank wet-weather operation in long sludge age WWTP. *Science of The Total Environment* 845: 157224.
- Geng H, Xu Y, Zheng L, et al. (2020) An overview of removing heavy metals from sewage sludge: Achievements and perspectives. *Environmental Pollution (Barking, Essex: 1987)* 266(Pt 2): 115375.
- Ghany HMA (2020) PRODUCTION OF A NEW ACTIVATED CARBON PREPARED FROM PALM FRONDS BY THERMAL ACTIVATION. *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research* 6(4): 34–43.
- Goala M, Yadav KK, Alam J, et al. (2021) Phytoremediation of dairy wastewater using *Azolla pinnata*: Application of image processing technique for leaflet growth simulation. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 42: 102152.
- González Y, Gómez G, Moeller-Chávez GE, et al. (2023) UV Disinfection Systems for Wastewater Treatment: Emphasis on Reactivation of Microorganisms. *Sustainability* 15(14): 11262.
- Goswami S and Das S (2015) A Study on Cadmium Phytoremediation Potential of Indian Mustard, *Brassica juncea*. *International Journal of Phytoremediation* 17(1–6): 583–588.
- Govarthanan M, Jeon C-H, Jeon Y-H, et al. (2020) Non-toxic nano approach for wastewater treatment using *Chlorella vulgaris* exopolysaccharides immobilized in iron-magnetic nanoparticles. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 162: 1241–1249.
- Granados P, Mireles S, Pereira E, et al. (2022) Effects of Biochar Production Methods and Biomass Types on Lead Removal from Aqueous Solution. *Applied Sciences* 12(10). 10. Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute: 5040.
- Guibaud G, van Hullebusch E and Bordas F (2006) Lead and cadmium biosorption by extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) extracted from activated sludges: pH-sorption edge tests and mathematical equilibrium modelling. *Chemosphere* 64(11): 1955–1962.
- Guittonny-Philippe A, Petit M-E, Masotti V, et al. (2015) Selection of wild macrophytes for use in constructed wetlands for phytoremediation of contaminant mixtures. *Journal of Environmental Management* 147: 108–123.
- Gul S, Gani KM, Govender I, et al. (2021) Reclaimed wastewater as an ally to global freshwater sources: a PESTEL evaluation of the barriers. *Journal of Water Supply: Research and Technology-Aqua* 70(2): 123–137.
- Guz Ł, Łagód G, Jaromin-Gleń K, et al. (2015) Application of Gas Sensor Arrays in Assessment of Wastewater Purification Effects. *Sensors* 15(1). 1. Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute: 1–21.
- Gwenzi W, Chaukura N, Noubactep C, et al. (2017) Biochar-based water treatment systems as a potential low-cost and sustainable technology for clean water provision. *Journal of Environmental Management* 197: 732–749.
- Hansen R, Thogersen T and Rogalla F (2007) Comparing cost and process performance of activated sludge (AS) and biological aerated filters (BAF) over ten years of full scale operation. *Water Science and Technology: A Journal of the International Association on Water Pollution Research* 55(8–9): 99–106.
- Haripriyan U, Gopinath KP, Arun J, et al. (2022) Bioremediation of organic pollutants: a mini review on current and critical strategies for wastewater treatment. *Archives of Microbiology* 204(5): 286.
- Hasan GM, Anwar S, Shamsi A, et al. (2024) The neuroprotective potential of phytochemicals in traumatic brain injury: mechanistic insights and pharmacological implications. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 14: 1330098.
- Hassaan M and El Nemr A (2017) Health and Environmental Impacts of Dyes: Mini Review. *American Journal of Environmental Science and Engineering* 1: 64–67.

- He L, Zhang Yong, Song D, et al. (2022) Influence of Pretreatment System on Inorganic Suspended Solids for Influent in Wastewater Treatment Plant. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health* Li T (ed.) 2022(1): 2768883.
- Heidari G and Kordbacheh F (2023) Pollutants and Approaches for their Removal from Water. *Materials Chemistry Horizons* (Online First). Epub ahead of print July 2023. DOI: 10.22128/mch.2023.684.1039.
- Hernández-Chover V, Castellet-Viciano L, Fuentes R, et al. (2023) Circular economy and efficiency to ensure the sustainability in the wastewater treatment plants. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 384: 135563.
- Hu Y, Peng Y, Liu W, et al. (2020) Removal of Emerging Contaminants from Water and Wastewater Using Nanofiltration Technology: In: Management Association IR (ed.) *Waste Management*. IGI Global, pp. 697–716. Available at: <http://services.igi-global.com/resolvedoi/resolve.aspx?doi=10.4018/978-1-7998-1210-4.ch033> (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Hussain S, Sajini AA, Blanco S, et al. (2013) NSun2-Mediated Cytosine-5 Methylation of Vault Noncoding RNA Determines Its Processing into Regulatory Small RNAs. *Cell Reports* 4(2): 255–261.
- Iftikhar J, Wang J, Wang Q, et al. (2017) Highly Efficient Lead Distribution by Magnetic Sewage Sludge Biochar: Sorption Mechanisms and Bench Applications. *Bioresource Technology* 238: 399–406.
- Islam T, Li Y and Cheng H (2021) Biochars and Engineered Biochars for Water and Soil Remediation: A Review. *Sustainability* 13(17): 9932.
- J W, D H, X L, et al. (2018) Remediation of As(III) and Cd(II) co-contamination and its mechanism in aqueous systems by a novel calcium-based magnetic biochar. *Journal of hazardous materials* 348. *J Hazard Mater*.
- Jayakumar A, Wurzer C, Soldatou S, et al. (2021) New directions and challenges in engineering biologically-enhanced biochar for biological water treatment. *Science of The Total Environment* 796: 148977.
- Jiang D, Matsushita B, Pahlevan N, et al. (2023) Estimating the concentration of total suspended solids in inland and coastal waters from Sentinel-2 MSI: A semi-analytical approach. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 204: 362–377.
- Jones ER, Van Vliet MTH, Qadir M, et al. (2021) Country-level and gridded estimates of wastewater production, collection, treatment and reuse. *Earth System Science Data* 13(2): 237–254.
- Joseph TM, Al-Hazmi HE, Śniatała B, et al. (2023) Nanoparticles and nanofiltration for wastewater treatment: From polluted to fresh water. *Environmental Research* 238(Pt 1): 117114.
- Kaetzl K, Lübken M, Uzun G, et al. (2019) On-farm wastewater treatment using biochar from local agroresidues reduces pathogens from irrigation water for safer food production in developing countries. *Science of The Total Environment* 682: 601–610.
- Karigar CS and Rao SS (2011) Role of microbial enzymes in the bioremediation of pollutants: a review. *Enzyme Research* 2011: 805187.
- Kaur H and Garg N (2021) Zinc toxicity in plants: a review. *Planta* 253(6): 129.
- Kawahigashi H (2009) Transgenic plants for phytoremediation of herbicides. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology* 20(2): 225–230.
- Khajvand M, Mostafazadeh AK, Drogui P, et al. (2022) Management of greywater: environmental impact, treatment, resource recovery, water recycling, and decentralization. *Water Science and Technology* 86(5): 909–937.
- Khan S and Malik A (2014) Environmental and Health Effects of Textile Industry Wastewater. In: Malik A, Grohmann E, and Akhtar R (eds) *Environmental Deterioration and Human Health*. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, pp. 55–71. Available at: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-94-007-7890-0_4 (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Khandare RV and Govindwar SP (2015) Phytoremediation of textile dyes and effluents: Current scenario and future prospects. *Biotechnology Advances* 33(8): 1697–1714.
- Khatri N, Vyas AK, Abdul-Qawy ASH, et al. (2023) Artificial neural network based models for predicting the effluent quality of a combined upflow anaerobic sludge blanket and facultative pond:

- Performance evaluation and comparison of different algorithms. *Environmental Research* 217: 114843.
- Kim Y-O, Safdar M, Kang H, et al. (2024) Glycine-Rich RNA-Binding Protein AtGRP7 Functions in Nickel and Lead Tolerance in Arabidopsis. *Plants* 13(2): 187.
- Kishor R, Purchase D, Saratale GD, et al. (2021) Ecotoxicological and health concerns of persistent coloring pollutants of textile industry wastewater and treatment approaches for environmental safety. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* 9(2): 105012.
- Klasson KT, Ledbetter CA, Uchimiya M, et al. (2013) Activated biochar removes 100 % dibromochloropropane from field well water. *Environmental Chemistry Letters* 11(3): 271–275.
- Krishnan RY, Manikandan S, Subbaiya R, et al. (2023) Recent approaches and advanced wastewater treatment technologies for mitigating emerging microplastics contamination - A critical review. *The Science of the Total Environment* 858(Pt 1): 159681.
- Kumar S and Deswal S (2020) Phytoremediation capabilities of *Salvinia molesta*, water hyacinth, water lettuce, and duckweed to reduce phosphorus in rice mill wastewater. *International Journal of Phytoremediation* 22(11): 1097–1109.
- Kunze M, Zerlin KF, Retzlaff A, et al. (2009) Degradation of chloroaromatics by *Pseudomonas putida* GJ31: assembled route for chlorobenzene degradation encoded by clusters on plasmid pKW1 and the chromosome. *Microbiology (Reading, England)* 155(Pt 12): 4069–4083.
- Kuo EY, Yang R-Y, Chin YY, et al. (2022) Multiomics approaches and genetic engineering of metabolism for improved biorefinery and wastewater treatment in microalgae. *Biotechnology Journal* 17(8): e2100603.
- Kurniawan TA, Haider A, Mohyuddin A, et al. (2023) Tackling microplastics pollution in global environment through integration of applied technology, policy instruments, and legislation. *Journal of Environmental Management* 346: 118971.
- Lavilla I, Cabaleiro N and Bendicho C (2018) Main Chemical Contaminants in Cosmetics. In: *Analysis of Cosmetic Products*. Elsevier, pp. 331–383. Available at: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/B978044463508200014X> (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Liu S, Liu YK, Lo KC, et al. (2024) Intelligent techniques and optimization algorithms in textile colour management: a systematic review of applications and prediction accuracy. *Fashion and Textiles* 11(1): 13.
- Loh ZZ, Zaidi NS, Yong EL, et al. (2022) Current Status and Future Research Trends of Biofiltration in Wastewater Treatment: a Bibliometric Review. *Current Pollution Reports* 8(3): 234–248.
- Lonappan L, Liu Y, Rouissi T, et al. (2018) Covalent immobilization of laccase on citric acid functionalized micro-biochars derived from different feedstock and removal of diclofenac. *Chemical Engineering Journal* 351: 985–994.
- Machineni L (2019) Review on biological wastewater treatment and resources recovery: attached and suspended growth systems. *Water Science and Technology: A Journal of the International Association on Water Pollution Research* 80(11): 2013–2026.
- Mateo-Sagasta J, Raschid-Sally L and Thebo A (2015) Global Wastewater and Sludge Production, Treatment and Use. In: Drechsel P, Qadir M, and Wichelns D (eds) *Wastewater*. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, pp. 15–38. Available at: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-94-017-9545-6_2 (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Matesun J, Petrik L, Musvoto E, et al. (2024) Limitations of wastewater treatment plants in removing trace anthropogenic biomarkers and future directions: A review. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 281: 116610.
- Meagher RB (2000) Phytoremediation of toxic elemental and organic pollutants. *Current Opinion in Plant Biology* 3(2): 153–162.
- Meena MD, Dotaniya ML, Meena BL, et al. (2023) Municipal solid waste: Opportunities, challenges and management policies in India: A review. *Waste Management Bulletin* 1(1): 4–18.
- Mehta J, Dhaka RK, Dilbaghi N, et al. (2024) Recent advancements in adsorptive removal of organophosphate pesticides from aqueous phase using nanomaterials. *Journal of Nanostructure in Chemistry* 14(1): 53–70.

- Mishra S, Kumar R and Kumar M (2023) Use of treated sewage or wastewater as an irrigation water for agricultural purposes- Environmental, health, and economic impacts. *Total Environment Research Themes* 6: 100051.
- Mkandawire M, Taubert B and Dudel EG (2004) Capacity of Lemna gibba L. (duckweed) for uranium and arsenic phytoremediation in mine tailing waters. *International Journal of Phytoremediation* 6(4): 347–362.
- Mohanty SK, Cantrell KB, Nelson KL, et al. (2014) Efficacy of biochar to remove Escherichia coli from stormwater under steady and intermittent flow. *Water Research* 61: 288–296.
- Molinos-Senante M, Reif R, Garrido-Baserba M, et al. (2013) Economic valuation of environmental benefits of removing pharmaceutical and personal care products from WWTP effluents by ozonation. *The Science of the Total Environment* 461–462: 409–415.
- Morris JC, Georgiou I, Guenther E, et al. (2021) Barriers in Implementation of Wastewater Reuse: Identifying the Way Forward in Closing the Loop. *Circular Economy and Sustainability* 1(1): 413–433.
- Mukhtar K, Asgher M, Afghan S, et al. (2010) Comparative study on two commercial strains of Saccharomyces cerevisiae for optimum ethanol production on industrial scale. *Journal of Biomedicine & Biotechnology* 2010: 419586.
- Mustafa HM and Hayder G (2021) Recent studies on applications of aquatic weed plants in phytoremediation of wastewater: A review article. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal* 12(1): 355–365.
- Naing AH, Park DY, Park HC, et al. (2023) Removal of heavy metals using Iris species: A potential approach for reclamation of heavy metal-polluted sites and environmental beautification. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research International* 30(32): 78004–78016.
- Naseema Rasheed R, Pourbakhtiar A, Mehdizadeh Allaf M, et al. (2023) Microalgal co-cultivation - recent methods, trends in omic-studies, applications, and future challenges. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology* 11. *Frontiers*.
- Nasr M, Ateia M and Hassan K (2016) Artificial intelligence for greywater treatment using electrocoagulation process. *Separation Science and Technology* 51(1): 96–105.
- Nishat A, Yusuf M, Qadir A, et al. (2023) Wastewater treatment: A short assessment on available techniques. *Alexandria Engineering Journal* 76: 505–516.
- Obaideen K, Shehata N, Sayed ET, et al. (2022) The role of wastewater treatment in achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs) and sustainability guideline. *Energy Nexus* 7: 100112.
- Oh K, Cao T, Li T, et al. (2014) Study on Application of Phytoremediation Technology in Management and Remediation of Contaminated Soils. *Journal of Clean Energy Technologies*: 216–220.
- Okan B, Erguder TH and Aksoy A (2023) Plant-wide modeling of a metropolitan wastewater treatment plant to reduce energy consumption and carbon footprint. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research International* 30(6): 16068–16080.
- Okeke NE, Adetunji CO, Nwankwo W, et al. (2021) A Critical Review of Microbial Transport in Effluent Waste and Sewage Sludge Treatment. In: Adetunji CO, Panpatte DG, and Jhala YK (eds) *Microbial Rejuvenation of Polluted Environment. Microorganisms for Sustainability*. Singapore: Springer Singapore, pp. 217–238. Available at: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-981-15-7459-7_10 (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Olabi AG, Abdelghafar AA, Maghrabie HM, et al. (2023) Application of artificial intelligence for prediction, optimization, and control of thermal energy storage systems. *Thermal Science and Engineering Progress* 39: 101730.
- Othmani B, Rasteiro MG and Khadhraoui M (2020) Toward green technology: a review on some efficient model plant-based coagulants/flocculants for freshwater and wastewater remediation. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy* 22(5): 1025–1040.
- Pandey VC, Singh JS, Singh DP, et al. (2014) Methanotrophs: promising bacteria for environmental remediation. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 11(1): 241–250.
- Park J-H, Wang JJ, Kim S-H, et al. (2019) Cadmium adsorption characteristics of biochars derived using various pine tree residues and pyrolysis temperatures. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* 553: 298–307.

- Parnian A, Chorom M, Jaafarzadeh N, et al. (2016) Use of two aquatic macrophytes for the removal of heavy metals from synthetic medium. *Ecohydrology & Hydrobiology* 16(3): 194–200.
- Paz-Ferreiro J, Lu H, Fu S, et al. (2013) Use of phytoremediation and biochar to remediate heavy metal polluted soils: a review. *Soil System Science*. Available at: <https://se.copernicus.org/articles/5/65/2014/se-5-65-2014-discussion.html> (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Peng Y, Tong W, Xie Y, et al. (2021) Yeast biomass-induced Co₂P/biochar composite for sulfonamide antibiotics degradation through peroxymonosulfate activation. *Environmental Pollution (Barking, Essex: 1987)* 268(Pt B): 115930.
- Perez-Mercado LF, Lalander C, Joel A, et al. (2019) Biochar filters as an on-farm treatment to reduce pathogens when irrigating with wastewater-polluted sources. *Journal of Environmental Management* 248: 109295.
- Pistocchi A, Andersen HR, Bertanza G, et al. (2022) Treatment of micropollutants in wastewater: Balancing effectiveness, costs and implications. *Science of The Total Environment* 850: 157593.
- Pradhananga R, Adhikari L, Shrestha R, et al. (2017) Wool Carpet Dye Adsorption on Nanoporous Carbon Materials Derived from Agro-Product. *C* 3(2): 12.
- Pratas J, Prasad MNV, Freitas H, et al. (2004) Plants growing in abandoned mines of Portugal are useful for biogeochemical exploration of arsenic, antimony, tungsten and mine reclamation. *Journal of Geochemical Exploration* 85(3): 99–107.
- Qadir M, Drechsel P, Jiménez Cisneros B, et al. (2020) Global and regional potential of wastewater as a water, nutrient and energy source. *Natural Resources Forum* 44(1): 40–51.
- Qasem NAA, Mohammed RH and Lawal DU (2021) Removal of heavy metal ions from wastewater: a comprehensive and critical review. *npj Clean Water* 4(1): 36.
- Qiao J, Liu T, Wang X, et al. (2018) Simultaneous alleviation of cadmium and arsenic accumulation in rice by applying zero-valent iron and biochar to contaminated paddy soils. *Chemosphere* 195: 260–271.
- Rajapaksha AU, Chen SS, Tsang DCW, et al. (2016) Engineered/designer biochar for contaminant removal/immobilization from soil and water: Potential and implication of biochar modification. *Chemosphere* 148: 276–291.
- Rathore P, Killedar DJ, Parde D, et al. (2022) Life cycle cost analysis of wastewater treatment technologies. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 1032(1): 012006.
- Regkouzas P, Asimakoulas I, Athanasiadou E, et al. (2025) The role of biochar in a circular economy: from agriculture to water and wastewater treatment applications. Available at: <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU24/EGU24-6788.html> (accessed 28 May 2025).
- Rogowska J, Cieszynska-Semenowicz M, Ratajczyk W, et al. (2020) Micropollutants in treated wastewater. *Ambio* 49(2): 487–503.
- Rosemarin A, Macura B, Carolus J, et al. (2020) Circular nutrient solutions for agriculture and wastewater – a review of technologies and practices. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 45: 78–91.
- Rout PR, Zhang TC, Bhunia P, et al. (2021) Treatment technologies for emerging contaminants in wastewater treatment plants: A review. *The Science of the Total Environment* 753: 141990.
- Ruiz LM, Pérez JI and Gómez MA (2023) Practical review of modelling and simulation applications at full-scale wastewater treatment plants. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 56: 104477.
- Saeed MU, Hussain N, Sumrin A, et al. (2022) Microbial bioremediation strategies with wastewater treatment potentialities – A review. *Science of The Total Environment* 818: 151754.
- Saikia M, Fu Y, Pavon-Eternod M, et al. (2010) Genome-wide analysis of N¹-methyl-adenosine modification in human tRNAs. *RNA* 16(7): 1317–1327.
- Scanlon BR, Fakhreddine S, Rateb A, et al. (2023) Author Correction: Global water resources and the role of groundwater in a resilient water future. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment* 4(5): 351–351.
- Schier W, Frechen F-B and Fischer St (2009) Efficiency of mechanical pre-treatment on European MBR plants. *Desalination* 236(1–3): 85–93.

- Sforza E, Kumkum P, Barbera E, et al. (2020) Bioremediation of industrial effluents: How a biochar pretreatment may increase the microalgal growth in tannery wastewater. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 37: 101431.
- Shabani N and Sayadi MH (2012) Evaluation of heavy metals accumulation by two emergent macrophytes from the polluted soil: an experimental study. *The Environmentalist* 32(1): 91–98.
- Shahid M, Austruy A, Echevarria G, et al. (2014) EDTA-Enhanced Phytoremediation of Heavy Metals: A Review. *Soil and Sediment Contamination: An International Journal* 23(4): 389–416.
- Shehzadi M, Afzal M, Khan MU, et al. (2014) Enhanced degradation of textile effluent in constructed wetland system using *Typha domingensis* and textile effluent-degrading endophytic bacteria. *Water Research* 58: 152–159.
- Shirkoohi MG, Tyagi RD, Vanrolleghem PA, et al. (2022) Artificial intelligence techniques in electrochemical processes for water and wastewater treatment: a review. *Journal of Environmental Health Science and Engineering* 20(2): 1089–1109.
- Siegelmann HT, Horne BG and Giles CL (1997) Computational capabilities of recurrent NARX neural networks. *IEEE transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics. Part B, Cybernetics: a publication of the IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society* 27(2): 208–215.
- Sijm-Eeken M, Jaspers M and Peute L (2023) Identifying Environmental Impact Factors for Sustainable Healthcare: A Scoping Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 20(18): 6747.
- Silva JA (2023) Wastewater Treatment and Reuse for Sustainable Water Resources Management: A Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability* 15(14): 10940.
- Simon-Várhelyi M, Cristea VM and Luca AV (2020) Reducing energy costs of the wastewater treatment plant by improved scheduling of the periodic influent load. *Journal of Environmental Management* 262: 110294.
- Singh R, Tripathi RD, Dwivedi S, et al. (2010) Lead bioaccumulation potential of an aquatic macrophyte *Najas indica* are related to antioxidant system. *Bioresource Technology* 101(9): 3025–3032.
- Singh S, Kumar V, Upadhyay N, et al. (2017) Efficient biodegradation of acephate by *Pseudomonas pseudoalcaligenes* PS-5 in the presence and absence of heavy metal ions [Cu(II) and Fe(III)], and humic acid. *3 Biotech* 7(4): 262.
- Singh S, Kumar Vijay, Romero R, et al. (2019) Applications of Nanoparticles in Wastewater Treatment. In: Prasad R, Kumar Vivek, Kumar M, et al. (eds) *Nanobiotechnology in Bioformulations. Nanotechnology in the Life Sciences*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 395–418. Available at: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-030-17061-5_17 (accessed 29 May 2025).
- Singha NA, Neihial R, Kipgen L, et al. (2023) Taxonomic and Predictive Functional Profile of Hydrocarbonoclastic Bacterial Consortia Developed at Three Different Temperatures. *Current Microbiology* 81(1): 22.
- Sinthusith N, Terada A, Hahn M, et al. (2015) Identification and quantification of bacteria and archaea responsible for ammonia oxidation in different activated sludge of full-scale wastewater treatment plants. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health. Part A, Toxic/Hazardous Substances & Environmental Engineering* 50(2): 169–175.
- Šoštarić TD, Petrović MS, Pastor FT, et al. (2018) Study of heavy metals biosorption on native and alkali-treated apricot shells and its application in wastewater treatment. *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 259: 340–349.
- Srivastav AL and Kaur T (2020) Factors affecting the formation of disinfection by-products in drinking water: human health risk. In: *Disinfection By-Products in Drinking Water*. Elsevier, pp. 433–450. Available at: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/B9780081029770000196> (accessed 29 May 2025).
- Sun P, Li Y, Meng T, et al. (2018) Removal of sulfonamide antibiotics and human metabolite by biochar and biochar/H₂O₂ in synthetic urine. *Water Research* 147: 91–100.
- Teles AGDX, Gomes EMV, Pokrywiecki JC, et al. (2024) Characterization and Ecotoxicity of Raw and Treated Liquid Effluent from the Washing of Soybean Seed Treatment Machines. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution* 235(1): 66.

- Thacharodi A, Meenatchi R, Hassan S, et al. (2023) Microplastics in the environment: A critical overview on its fate, toxicity, implications, management, and bioremediation strategies. *Journal of Environmental Management* 349: 119433.
- Tompkins D, Bumbac C, Clifford E, et al. (2019) EU Horizon 2020 Research for A Sustainable Future: INNOQUA—A Nature-Based Sanitation Solution. *Water* 11(12): 2461.
- Toyama T, Furukawa T, Maeda N, et al. (2011) Accelerated biodegradation of pyrene and benzo[a]pyrene in the *Phragmites australis* rhizosphere by bacteria–root exudate interactions. *Water Research* 45(4): 1629–1638.
- Tyagi U and Anand N (2023) Prospective of Waste Lignocellulosic Biomass as Precursors for the Production of Biochar: Application, Performance, and Mechanism—A Review. *BioEnergy Research* 16(3): 1335–1360.
- Global Wastewater Status Assessed from: <https://unu.edu/inweh/tools-and-resources/global-wastewater-status> on 15-5-2025.
- Valili S, Siavalas G, Karapanagioti HK, et al. (2013) Phenanthrene removal from aqueous solutions using well-characterized, raw, chemically treated, and charred malt spent rootlets, a food industry by-product. *Journal of Environmental Management* 128: 252–258.
- Van Welie MJ and Romijn HA (2018) NGOs fostering transitions towards sustainable urban sanitation in low-income countries: Insights from Transition Management and Development Studies. *Environmental Science & Policy* 84: 250–260.
- Varjani SJ and Upasani VN (2017) A new look on factors affecting microbial degradation of petroleum hydrocarbon pollutants. *International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation* 120: 71–83.
- Vidya Vijay M, Sudarsan JS and Nithiyantham S (2019) Sustainability of constructed wetlands using biochar as effective absorbent for treating wastewaters. *International Journal of Energy and Water Resources* 3(2): 153–164.
- Vigneshwaran S, Sirajudheen P, Karthikeyan P, et al. (2021) Fabrication of sulfur-doped biochar derived from tapioca peel waste with superior adsorption performance for the removal of Malachite green and Rhodamine B dyes. *Surfaces and Interfaces* 23: 100920.
- Villarín MC and Merel S (2020) Paradigm shifts and current challenges in wastewater management. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 390: 122139.
- Vysokomornaya OV, Kurilenko EYu and Shcherbinina AA (2015a) Major Contaminants in Industrial and Domestic Wastewater. *MATEC Web of Conferences Kuznetsov GV, Strizhak PA, Bulba EE, et al. (eds)* 23: 01041.
- Vysokomornaya OV, Kurilenko EYu and Shcherbinina AA (2015b) Major Contaminants in Industrial and Domestic Wastewater. *MATEC Web of Conferences Kuznetsov GV, Strizhak PA, Bulba EE, et al. (eds)* 23: 01041.
- Wang A, Lin C, Shen Z, et al. (2020) Effects of Pre-Oxidation on Haloacetonitrile and Trichloronitromethane Formation during Subsequent Chlorination of Nitrogenous Organic Compounds. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17(3): 1046.
- Wang Y, Cheng Y, Liu H, et al. (2023) A Review on Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Wastewater Treatment. *Sustainability* 15(18): 13557.
- Wei H, Tang Y, Li A, et al. (2019) Insights into the effects of acidification on sewage sludge dewaterability through pH repeated adjustment. *Chemosphere* 227: 269–276.
- Wilson NJ, Smith-Moore CM, Xu Y, et al. (2022) Introduction of a condensed, reverse tricarboxylic acid cycle for additional CO₂ fixation in plants. *Plant Biology*. Available at: <http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/2022.03.04.483018> (accessed 1 June 2025).
- Woolf D, Amonette JE, Street-Perrott FA, et al. (2010) Sustainable biochar to mitigate global climate change. *Nature Communications* 1(1): 56.
- Wu B, Liu F, Fang W, et al. (2021) Microbial sulfur metabolism and environmental implications. *The Science of the Total Environment* 778: 146085.
- Wuhrmann K, Mechsner KI and Kappeler Th (1980) Investigation on rate — Determining factors in the microbial reduction of azo dyes. *European journal of applied microbiology and biotechnology* 9(4): 325–338.

- Yang F, Zhang S, Sun Y, et al. (2018) Fabrication and characterization of hydrophilic corn stalk biochar-supported nanoscale zero-valent iron composites for efficient metal removal. *Bioresource Technology* 265: 490–497.
- Yenkie KM (2019) Integrating the three E's in wastewater treatment: efficient design, economic viability, and environmental sustainability. *Current Opinion in Chemical Engineering* 26: 131–138.
- Yoshida A (1975) Purification of human red cell glucose 6-phosphate dehydrogenase by affinity chromatography. *Journal of Chromatography* 114(2): 321–327.
- Yuan Q, Wang P, Wang X, et al. (2022) Phytoremediation of cadmium-contaminated sediment using *Hydrilla verticillata* and *Elodea canadensis* harbor two same keystone rhizobacteria *Pedospaeraceae* and *Parasegetibacter*. *Chemosphere* 286(Pt 1): 131648.
- Zahmatkesh S, Hajiaghaei-Keshteli M, Bokhari A, et al. (2023) Wastewater treatment with nanomaterials for the future: A state-of-the-art review. *Environmental Research* 216(Pt 3): 114652.
- Zailani S and Sarvajayakesavalu S (eds) (2023) *Solid Waste and Landfills Management - Recent Advances*. IntechOpen. Available at: <https://www.intechopen.com/books/11530> (accessed 29 May 2025).
- Zarzycki M, Morrison V, Bei E, et al. (2023) Cultural and societal motivations for being informal caregivers: a qualitative systematic review and meta-synthesis. *Health Psychology Review* 17(2): 247–276.
- Zhang B, Yu Q, Yan G, et al. (2018) Seasonal bacterial community succession in four typical wastewater treatment plants: correlations between core microbes and process performance. *Scientific Reports* 8(1): 4566.
- Zhang J-G, Zhang F, Thakur K, et al. (2017) Valorization of Spent *Escherichia coli* Media Using Green Microalgae *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* and Feedstock Production. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 8: 1026.
- Zhang P, Yang M, Lan J, et al. (2023) Water Quality Degradation Due to Heavy Metal Contamination: Health Impacts and Eco-Friendly Approaches for Heavy Metal Remediation. *Toxics* 11(10): 828.
- Zhao Q, Xu T, Song X, et al. (2021) Preparation and Application in Water Treatment of Magnetic Biochar. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology* 9. *Frontiers*.
- Zheng W, Guo M, Chow T, et al. (2010) Sorption properties of greenwaste biochar for two triazine pesticides. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 181(1–3): 121–126.
- Zhou Y, Liu X, Xiang Y, et al. (2017) Modification of biochar derived from sawdust and its application in removal of tetracycline and copper from aqueous solution: Adsorption mechanism and modelling. *Bioresource Technology* 245(Pt A): 266–273.
- Zhuang W-Q, Fitts JP, Ajo-Franklin CM, et al. (2015) Recovery of critical metals using biometallurgy. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology* 33: 327–335.
- Zimmerman AE, Howard-Varona C, Needham DM, et al. (2020) Metabolic and biogeochemical consequences of viral infection in aquatic ecosystems. *Nature Reviews. Microbiology* 18(1): 21–34.

Author Contributions

MV, SJ, and JK conceived the idea of this review article. SJ, JK, AJ, DR, and MV performed the analysis and drafted the manuscript. SJ, JK and MV supported the interpretation of data from the literature and revision of the manuscript. SJ and MV critically reviewed the manuscript. All the authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Acknowledgements

SJ acknowledges Principal, Miranda House, University of Delhi; JK acknowledges Principal, Maitreyi College, University of Delhi; and AJ, DR, MV acknowledge Principal, Hansraj college, University of Delhi for constantly encouraging this research.

Funding

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Open Access *This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution, and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. Visit for more details <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.*

Citation: Jit S, Kaur J, Jain A, Raina D and Verma M (2025) Advancing Wastewater Management: Policies and Sustainable Solutions for Global Water Security. *Environmental Science Archives* 4(1): 324-350.